

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF A PONTOON

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Declaration

The thesis titled "*Structural analysis of a pontoon by Maestro*", submitted by *Papia Sultana* (0812008) and *Md. Mottakenur Rahman* (0812005) has been accepted as satisfactory in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of ***BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN NAVAL ARCHITECTURE & MARINE ENGINEERING.***

.....

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Candidate's declaration

It is hereby declared that this thesis or any part of it has not been submitted elsewhere for any degree or diploma.

Papia Sultana (0812008)

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To Our Parents

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ABSTRACT

In this thesis, the design of a Pontoon is done which is directly & entirely based on structural theory & computer-based method of analysis is applied. For this purpose, a rationally-based design software Maestro is used. The findings of the analysis are the deflections of the model under applied load of the design bending moment 10901.5257N-m which is found by weight distribution of the pontoon by Tabular method, stress distribution of the model including shear stress, normal stress, Von Misses stress is also found . The maximum displacement of the pontoon is found 0.0013823m, which occurs in the midship. The seriousness of structural damage is assessed & the structural adequacy of the design is checked. The bending moment analysis is done manually which is than compared to the values found by the software to check the validity of the result. Thus, the response analysis of the structure for the loads on the overall structure is checked to the limit state condition in which a structure or a structural member has become unfit for one of its intended role due to one or more load effects.

“It had long since come to my attention that people of accomplishment rarely sat back and let things happen to them. They went out and happened to things.”

Leonardo da Vinci

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1: Motivation

MAESTRO is a design, analysis, and evaluation tool specifically tailored for floating structures & marine structures. At MAESTRO's core is a structural design tool developed to suit the needs of ship designers and naval architects. MAESTRO offers numerous ship-based loading patterns (e.g., Basic Loads: Cargo Loads, Liquid Tank Loads; Sea Environment: Hull Girder Loads/Sea Loads/Ship Motion Loads; Operational Loads: Slamming/Flooding/Docking; and Combat Environment: Shock/Air Blast/Weapons Effects) to accurately and efficiently produce the necessary load cases. In addition to calculating stresses and displacements using the finite element analysis method, MAESTRO can also perform an automatic failure evaluation of the principal structural members. MAESTRO can also interface directly with NAPA in order to leverage existing geometry and loading information. The evaluation procedure can be shown as the:

Table 1: algorithm of structural analysis procedure.

1.2: Objective of the thesis

- To understand the physical behaviors as strength of the structure by FEM method.
- To predict the performance and behavior of the structure, to calculate the safety margin; and to identify the weakness of the design accurately.
- Deformation of the structure can be viewed after the application of the load.
- Stress distribution can be seen including shear stress, normal stress, Von-Mises stress etc.
- Optimization of the structure can be done by iterating the self-weight of the structure changing the spacing of different structural members as stiffeners, longitudinal etc.

1.3: Overview of the thesis

- Chapter 1 provides an introduction and motivation for the use of Maestro software in Ship Design Process and defines the thesis objectives.
- Chapter 2 provides the literature review of works on Maestro software.
- Chapter 3 provides a brief description of the numerical scheme of the computational method& the steps of the process used in the thesis.
- Chapter 4 provides mathematical formulation of the 3d model of the structure& setting the parameters i.e. material properties, element properties.
- Chapter 5 comprises the construction procedure of the geometry of the structure i.e. creating the strakes layout of modules
- Chapter 6 describes the verification of design parameters to the required value& several integrity checks of the model.
- Chapter 7 describes the calculation of design bending moment from weight & buoyancy distribution of the pontoon using tabular method.
- Chapter 8 provides how the structure is stabilized such as applying constraints, loads, balancing the model for solving.
- Chapter 9 describes the analysis & evaluation of the structure.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1: History

The Aeronautical & Ocean Engineering Department is the home of the computer program MAESTRO (Method for Analysis, Evaluation and Structural Optimization). Developed by Prof. Hughes, MAESTRO performs first-principles structural design of innovative and high performance vehicles such as high speed ferries, multihull ships and warships. MAESTRO is used by 13 navies, by various structural safety authorities, and by over 80 structural designers and shipyards in Europe, North America, Asia, and Australia. It is also a valuable research tool, and it is the basis for three ONR-sponsored research projects to develop improved naval ships of the future. The overall objective is to produce structural design methods and algorithms for advanced naval ships that can achieve significant savings and advantageous tradeoffs in the conflicting attributes of structural weight, safety, and survivability.

2.2 Previous works on maestro

Design of Ballistic Missile Defense Submarine is done on maestro, which describes the Concept Exploration and Development of a Diesel/ AIP Ballistic Missile Defense Submarine (SSBMD) for the United States Navy. This project is based on the need to provide a sea-based ballistic missile defense launch capability to guard against rogue and hostile nation missile attack. The submarine platform allows for covert positioning near potential enemy launch sites and provides a favorable launch angle for missile interception with guidance from surface or air Bourne assets. In MAESTRO the dimensions of the submarine was altered to save weight and bring the adequacies closer to zero. Frame instability and lobar buckling were the critical limit states or modes of failure. When the loads were applied a course mesh FEA is run using the MAESTRO COM Solver, which outputs the stress results. Display of the Von Mises Stress was obtained which is the stress combination at a given point that will cause failure; however, it is not the limiting mode of failure in this submarine. Although the stresses appear in red, they are still approximately one-third of the yield stress. Frame instability and lobar buckling were only calculated manually and remained the critical limit states.

Medium Surface Combatant (MSC) design was also done in Maestro. The MSC requirement is based on the MSC Initial Capabilities Document (ICD) and the MSC Acquisition Decision Memorandum. Concept Exploration trade-off studies and design space exploration are accomplished using a Multi-Objective Genetic Optimization (MOGO) after significant technology research and definition. Objective attributes for this optimization are cost, risk (technology, cost, schedule and performance) and military effectiveness. The product of this optimization is a series of cost-risk-effectiveness frontiers which are used to select alternative designs and define Operational Requirements (ORD1) based on the customer's preference for cost, risk and effectiveness. When the ship model is in the detailed design phase it is analyzed in MAESTRO which runs a structural breakdown of the vessel and identifies any local buckling or structural concerns. Evaluation in MAESTRO determines if the scantlings are acceptable. Scantling dimensions are changed in an iterative process until an acceptable adequacy is obtained.

Rational ship structural design needs stress analyses to be carried out with a certain degree of approximation: this means an adequate representation of ship structures and realistic assumption on loads combinations. As far as structural modeling is concerned finite element models for the stress analysis of the whole ship are more and more frequently adopted, allowing good insight in structural behavior. Because of uncertainties of the loads the ship has to withstand during her life, the effectiveness of direct calculation considerably depends not only on goodness of structural modeling, but also on the evaluation of environmental loads and ways to apply them on structures. MAESTRO contains a specific routine for ultimate bending moment evaluation based on the Adamchak's approach. The ultimate strength evaluation can be integrated into the MAESTRO design process in two ways: as a final check of the design or as an obligatory step, and as a possible constraint, in an optimization process. The knowledge of realistic loading histories shall contribute not only in checking the ship response to extreme loads, but will be also extremely important to investigate the fatigue behavior of structures due to the cumulative contribution of all significant cyclic loads. In fact most common structural problems experienced by ships after prolonged operations at sea consist in fatigue crack-ing; although generally fatigue cracks do not represent a safety problems, they can originate considerable costs for repair.

CHAPTER 3

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

In consideration of the overall ship structural loading & response, the ship is idealized as a hollow thin-wall box beam, referring the ‘hull girder’ which acts according to the simple beam theory. The hull girder is assumed to be elastic, its deflections are small & the longitudinal strain due to bending varies linearly over the cross section, at neutral axis there is zero strain.

For overall static equilibrium requires that the total upwards buoyancy force equals the weight of the ship & these two vertical forces coincide i.e. the longitudinal center of buoyancy (LCB) must coincide with the longitudinal center of gravity (LCG). For the first requirement using the notation

$$\begin{aligned} \rho g \int_0^L a(x) dx &= g \int_0^L m(x) dx \\ &= g \Delta \end{aligned}$$

Where, $a(x)$ = immersed cross-sectional area

$m(x)$ = mass distribution

ρ = mass density of sea water

g = gravitational acceleration

Δ = displacement

The factor g is retained on both sides to emphasize that it is forces which are involved.

For the equilibrium of moments, the equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho g \int_0^L a(x)x dx &= g \int_0^L m(x)x dx \\ &= g \Delta I_G \end{aligned}$$

Where, I_G = distance from origin to LCG

In elastic, small-deflection beam theory the governing equation for the bending moment $M(x)$ is

$$d^2M/dx^2 = f(x)$$

$f(x)$ is the loading on the beam, expressed as a distributed vertical force. For a ship this is a net distributed force i.e. it is the net resultant of the buoyancy force $b(x)$ & the weight force $w(x)$. In the sign convention adopted herein forces are positive upward, but an exception is made for the weight force which is conventionally regarded as positive. Hence the net force is $f(x) = b(x) - w(x)$. The solution for $M(x)$

requires two integrations. The first yields the transverse shear force $Q(x)$ which is obtained by imposing vertical force equilibrium of a differential element considered as a free body.

$$Q + f dx - Q - dQ = 0$$

$$\text{Or, } f = dQ/dx$$

$$\text{From which, } Q(x) = \int_0^x f(x)dx + C$$

For ships the constant of integration is always zero because the hull girder is a 'free-free' beam, with zero shear force at the ends, $Q(0) = 0$

$$M + Q dx + f dx dx/2 - M - dM = 0$$

The dx^2 term is of second order & therefore

$$Q = dM/dx$$

$$\text{From which, } M(x) = \int_0^x Q(x)dx + C$$

Shear force at any point is positive if the integral or net accumulation, of load up to that point is positive. If we define a 'positive face' as the cross section which can be seen when looking in the positive x-direction, then the shear force is positive upward when acting on a positive face & positive downward when acting on a negative face.

Similarly, the bending moment at any point is positive if the integral, or net accumulation, of shear force up to that point is positive. It can easily be shown that with this definition, positive bending moment corresponds to beam curvature that is concave upward. This condition state of bending is referred to as "sagging" & the opposite state concave downward is referred to as "hogging".

This analysis entails the calculation of the effects of the environmental loads on the overall structure. For references the load effects will be represented by the symbol Q . A limit value is denoted by the symbol Q_L . the limit values are the values of the loads or load effects which produce or corresponds to a limit state. A limit state is a condition any condition in which a structure or a structural member has become unfit for one of its intended roles. The symbol Q_L represents the values of a group of loads which produce a limit state.

In accordance to dealing with statistical uncertainty, a rationally-based design procedure must also provide some means whereby the designer can explicitly allow for the other uncertainties. This is done by specifying a minimum value of the margin between Q & Q_L . in practice this margin is usually specified in terms of a safety factor γ which is the minimum factor by which Q_L must exceed Q . In terms of γ the constraint is of the form

$$\gamma Q \leq Q_L, \text{ this is the constraint equation}$$

Then the response analysis is checked with limit analysis & the value of safety factor is determined as following:

Table 2: comparison between the response analysis & limit analysis.

CHAPTER 4

NUMERICAL SCHEME

Computational method:

FEA as applied in engineering is a computational tool for performing engineering analysis. It includes the use of mesh generation techniques for dividing a complex problem into small elements. Finite element analysis (FEA) is a fairly recent discipline crossing the boundaries of mathematics, physics, engineering and computer science. The method has wide application and enjoys extensive utilization in the structural, thermal and fluid analysis areas. The finite element method is comprised of three major phases:

Pre-processing:

The goals of pre-processing are to develop an appropriate finite element mesh, assign suitable material properties, and apply boundary conditions in the form of restraints and loads. The finite element mesh subdivides the geometry into *elements*, upon which are found *nodes*. The nodes, which are really just point locations in space, are generally located at the element corners and perhaps near each mid-side.

Solver:

While the pre-processing and post-processing phases of the finite element method are interactive and time-consuming for the analyst, the solution is often a batch process, and is demanding of computer resource. The governing equations are assembled into matrix form and are solved numerically. The assembly process depends not only on the type of analysis (e.g. static or dynamic), but also on the model's element types and properties, material properties and boundary conditions.

Post-processing:

After a finite element model has been prepared and checked, boundary conditions have been applied, and the model has been solved, it is time to investigate the results of the analysis. This activity is known as the post-processing phase of the finite element method.

Post-processing begins with a thorough check for problems that may have occurred during solution. Most solvers provide a log file, which should be searched for warnings or errors, and which will also provide a quantitative measure of how well-behaved the numerical procedures were during solution. Next, reaction loads at restrained nodes should be summed and examined as a "sanity check". Reaction loads that do not closely balance the applied load resultant for a linear static analysis should cast doubt on the validity of other results. Error norms such as strain energy density and stress deviation among adjacent elements might be looked at next, but for h-code analyses these quantities are best used to target subsequent adaptive re-meshing.

CHAPTER 5

MODELING OF THE STRUCTURE

The General Arrangement & Midship drawing of the structure is given below:

Figure 1: Elevation of pontoon

Figure 2: main deck of pontoon

Figure 3: Ordinary frame

Figure 4: Web frame

Pontoon particulars:

Table 3: Principle particulars of a pontoon

LBP	20m
Half breadth	7.5m
Hull depth	2.5m
Design draft,full load	1.5m
Materials	Mild steel
Stiffeners/longitudinal/frames	T & L section
Transverse frame spacing	0.625m
Transverse WT BHD spacing	3.125m

As the pontoon is of transverse symmetry, we will only model only half part of it. Safety factor is taken 1.5.

After setting the units, we created our first substructure. A substructure is a set of modules that are generally associated with each other. For this particular pontoon, we divided the whole structure into 8 modules in bow, amidship & aft. All of the substructure & modules are created under the Top part, which is the fundamental highest level for the global coarse mesh model in MAESTRO. We give each module a different name as m1, m2 etc. & their origin location is specified, the location of the module is relative to the substructure location, which we defined as amidship as the global x origin. Each module is divided into equally spaced sections as 625 mm.

Now we input the material properties of mild steel:

Table 4: the material properties of mild steel

Young's modulus	204GPa
Poissons ratio	0.3
Density	7850kg/m ³
Yield stress	235MPa
Ultimate tensile stress	400MPa
Reduced yield stress at heat affected zone	235MPa
Weld residual stress	0
Structural proportional limit ratio	1
(NVR) allowable bending stress	188MPa

Our pontoon model requires 2types of element: plate element & beam element. We use plates of 3 different thicknesses as: 8mm.10mm & 10mm. Beam elements will represent the frame, longitudinal and stiffeners elements in our model. Here we use T & L types beam elements their properties are:

Table 5: Properties of stiffening members.

Name	Web height, m	Web thickness, m	Flange width, m	Flange thickness, m
T/tee	0.3	0.008	0.15	0.012
L/ angle	0.1	0.01	0.1	0.01

Table 6: Properties of plates.

Bottom Plates (length x thickness) , mm	Side Plates (length x thickness) , mm	Deck plates (length x thickness) , mm
1000 x 10	2000 x 10	1000 x 12
1000 x 10	500 x 12	1000 x 12
2000 x 10		2000 x 12
2000 x 10		2000 x 12
1500 x 10		1500 x 12

CHAPTER 6

CONSTRUCTION GEOMETRY OF THE STRUCTURE

At first we create the 3d structure of our model in Rhinoceros software.

Figure 5:3D model in Rhinoceros.

Then we import that .dxf file in Maestro. Now we build the modules, firstly by creating endpoints & nodes. The endpoint locations are laid out to capture the changes in plate thickness, section shape and intersection points. Then we add the stiffeners in the structure according to the mid-ship drawing of the pontoon. Stiffeners are defined as beam elements and are used to add additional stiffness in the defined direction. In a MAESTRO coarse mesh model, the stiffeners are not actual finite elements, but instead their properties are smeared into the stiffened quad element creating an orthotropic material. Stiffener layouts can be defined by a number of stiffeners per panel or a breadth between stiffeners. Edge stiffeners can also be added to either of the definition methods. After endpoints are created and our element properties are defined, we then create strakes. Strakes are a convenient way to create all of the structural elements as plates, frames, girders and stiffeners between two endpoints, utilizing the longitudinal symmetry between endpoints within a module. The location of the strake determines whether or not those plate elements will receive a hydrostatic pressure during the analysis. Locations of “bottom” or “side” will make the element “wetted”, whereas “deck” or “other” will not. Normally, all of the outside shell elements of a vessel will be “wetted” as they will see pressure from the water they are in. After creating strakes we then created watertight bulkheads at forward and aft bulkheads of the modules so that the model will not collapse at the ends once the load is applied. we used compound elements for this step. Compound elements provide a convenient method for quickly creating repetitive transverse structure. A prototype is created once and can be repeated along a module's longitudinal direction using the replication rule. Compound elements constructed using quadratic elements between the edges. After creating the transverse bulkheads we create a longitudinal bulkhead at 3.9m distance from the centerline. Repeating the above process we completed each of 8 modules comprising the structure.

Completion of the whole structure is shown following in respective steps:

Figure 6:m1 module (location from midship to 3.125m)

Figure 7:m2 module (location 3.125m to 6.25m)

Figure 9:m3 module (location 6.25m to 9.375m)

Figure 8:m4 module (location 9.375m t0 10m)

Figure 11:m5 module (location from midship to -3.125m)

Figure 10:m6 module (location from -3.125m to -6.25m)

Figure 13:m7 module (location from -6.25m to -9.375m)

Figure 12:m8 module (location from -9.375m to -10.0m)

Figure 14: complete model (rear view)

Figure 15: complete model (front view)

CHAPTER 7

VERIFICATION OF THE DESIGN PARAMETR

After the completion of module creation, we checked the design parameters i.e. section modulus, moment of inertia. From a visual check of the result, we can see that the value of I_{zz} is never less than 0.282459 m^4 in all sections & the value of section modulus ($I_{zz}/Y(+/-)$) is never less than 0.359958 m^3 .

After finishing the modeling stage, we performed some integrity checks on the model, after creating each module. Checks on Wetted elements, the side & bottom shells should be the wetted elements, our model satisfies this.

Figure 17: check on wetted elements

Connectivity checks, all elements must be connected, elements of our model are connected.

Figure 16: connectivity check of model

Checks on free edge, no free edge should exist in the model. A free edge occurs when not all the elements share common edges with each other. This usually occurs when a node is used by one element in a specific area but not by its neighboring element. Our model has no free edges.

Figure 18: free edge of model

Checks on aspect ratio, this check verifies that no element's aspect ratio is above a certain limit. Setting the threshold to 5.0 and we received a message stating no elements with an aspect ratio greater than 5.0 found.

Checks on overlapped elements, this check verifies that no elements were created on top of each other. We found some overlapped elements& we have deleted them.

CHAPTER 8

CALCULATION OF BENDING MOMENT

A bending moment is a measure of the average *internal stress* induced in a *structural element* when an *external force* or moment is applied to the element causing the element to bend.

The internal stresses in a cross-section of a structural element can be resolved into a resultant force and a resultant couple. For equilibrium, the moment created by external forces (and external moments) must be balanced by the couple induced by the internal stresses. The resultant internal couple is called the bending moment while the resultant internal force is called the shear force (if it is transverse to the plane of element) or the normal force (if it is along the plane of the element).

The bending moment at a section through a structural element may be defined as "the sum of the moments about that section of all external forces acting to one side of that section". The forces and moments on either side of the section must be equal in order to counteract each other and maintain a state of equilibrium so the same bending moment will result from summing the moments, regardless of which side of the section is selected. If clockwise bending moments are taken as negative, then a negative bending moment within an element will cause "sagging", and a positive moment will cause "hogging". It is therefore clear that a point of zero bending moment within a beam is a point of contra flexure—that is the point of transition from hogging to sagging or vice versa.

8.1: Weight distribution & weight curve

The Resultant internal forces which are known as shear force can be calculated from structure's load curve. The differences between buoyancy curve & weight curve is known as 'Load curve'. For weight distribution, the whole pontoon is divided into several sections and calculates the area of the sections with the help of GA drawing. The sections are like: Upper deck plate, bottom plate, bulkheads (longitudinal & Transverse), side shell plate, edge plate, frames (side, bottom, and upper), longitudinal (L& T section) etc. The calculated areas are multiplied by their thickness and the individual's volumes are calculated. The materials density, $\rho = 7850 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$ so the multiple of volume & density is weight distribution of each sections. The summation of weights is taken as total weight, which is **64696.1675 kg**.

Table 7: Weight distribution of structural members

Members	area	thickness	amount	volume	kg/m ³	weight ,Kg
deck plate	150	0.012	1	1.8	7850	14130
bottom plate	131.25	0.01	1	1.3125	7850	10303.125
inclined plate 1	12.99	0.01	1	0.1299	7850	1019.715
inclined plate 2	12.99	0.01	1	0.1299	7850	1019.715
side shell 1	48.5	0.01		0.485	7850	3807.25
long. BHD centre	48.5	0.01	1	0.485	7850	3807.25
long. BHD middle	48.5	0.01	1	0.485	7850	3807.25
trans. BHD 1	9.75	0.01	1	0.0975	7850	765.375
trans. bhd 2	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 3	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 4	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 5	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 6	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 7	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 8	18.75	0.01	1	0.1875	7850	1471.875
trans. bhd 9	9.75	0.01	1	0.0975	7850	765.375
floors	0.0042		23	0.7245	7850	5687.325
side frames	0.0001		23	0.00575	7850	45.1375
deck frame	0.0042		23	0.7245	7850	5687.325
for T(2)						
longitudinals bottom	0.0042		2	0.168	7850	1318.8
longitudinals side	0.0042		1	0.084	7850	659.4
longitudinal upper	0.0042		2	0.168	7850	1318.8
for L(8)						
longitudinals bottom	0.0001		8	0.016	7850	125.6
longitudinal upper	0.0001		8	0.016	7850	125.6
					Total=	64696.168

Table 8 : weight distribution at different sections of 1m length

0-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	5.0-6.0	6.0-7.0	7.0-8.0	8.0-9.0	9.0-10.0	10.0-11.0
6866.92	6526.4	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9

11.0-12.0	12.0-13.0	13.0-14.0	14.0-15.0	15.0-16.0	16.0-17.0	17.0-18.0	18.0-19.0	19.0-20.0
6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6412.9	6526.4	6866.92

Figure 19: Weight Curve

8.2: Buoyancy curve

Buoyancy is defined as the tendency of a fluid to exert a supporting upward force on a body placed in a fluid (i.e., a liquid or a gas). The fluid can be a liquid, as in the case of a boat floating on a lake. The buoyant force on the object determines whether or not a given object will sink or float in a fluid. The center of buoyancy of an object is the centroid of the displaced volume of fluid.

As buoyancy = weight of displaced fluid, so for determination of Buoyancy force of an floating structure, underwater volume is needed to know which can be calculated from underwater area, multiple by breadth. The underwater volume is multiplied by water density $\rho = 1000 \text{ kgm}^{-3}$ (fresh water) and buoyant force is calculated which is **64700 kg**. For stability buoyant force & total weight should be equal which is satisfied here on this pontoon. A graph is plotted with distributed buoyant force along with regular interval of length.

Table 9 : Buoyancy distribution at different sections of 1m length

0-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	5.0-6.0	6.0-7.0	7.0-8.0	8.0-9.0	9.0-10.0	10.0-11.0
325	6210	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.1875	7270.188
11.0-12.0	12.0-13.0	13.0-14.0	14.0-15.0	15.0-16.0	16.0-17.0	17.0-18.0	18.0-19.0	19.0-20.0		
7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	7270.188	6210	325		

Figure 20: Buoyancy Curve

8.3: Load curve

The difference between distributed buoyant force and distributed weight is *load*, which is plotted along the length and the curve is known as *Load curve*.

Table 10 : Load distribution at different sections of 1m length

0-1.0	1.0-2.0	2.0-3.0	3.0-4.0	4.0-5.0	5.0-6.0	6.0-7.0	7.0-8.0	8.0-9.0	9.0-10.0
6541.92	316.4	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288
11.0-12.0	12.0-13.0	13.0-14.0	14.0-15.0	15.0-16.0	16.0-17.0	17.0-18.0	18.0-19.0	19.0-20.0	11.0-12.0
-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	-857.288	316.4	6541.92

Figure 21: Load curve

8.4: Calculation of Shear force and Bending moment

Shearing forces are unaligned forces pushing one part of a body in one direction, and another part of the body in the opposite direction. The cumulative summation of loads along with pervious stations (half stations are considered too) will get shear forces and gradually shear area. The process eventually gives the bending moment area and bending moment. If these values are plotted against the length, then shear force and bending moment curve will produce.

Table 11: Calculation of Shear force & Bending moment

Stations	W	B	load	SF,kg	SF,areas	BM,areas	BM
0				0		0	0
0.5	6866.92	325	6541.92		6541.92		
1				6541.92		6541.92	3270.96
1.5	6526.4	6210	316.4		13400.24		
2				6858.32		19942.16	9971.08
2.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		12859.35		
3				6001.033		32801.51	16400.76
3.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		11144.78		
4				5143.745		43946.29	21973.15
4.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		9430.203		
5				4286.458		53376.49	26688.25
5.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		7715.628		
6				3429.17		61092.12	30546.06
6.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		6001.053	0	
7				2571.883		67093.17	33546.59
7.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		4286.478	0	
8				1714.595		71379.65	35689.83
8.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		2571.902	0	
9				857.3075		73951.55	36975.78
9.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		857.3275	0	
10				0.02		74808.88	37404.44
10.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-857.248	0	
11				-857.268		73951.63	36975.82
11.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-2571.82	0	
12				-1714.56		71379.81	35689.91
12.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-4286.4	0	
13				-2571.84		67093.41	33546.71
13.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-6000.97	0	
14				-3429.13		61092.44	30546.22
14.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-7715.55	0	
15				-4286.42		53376.89	26688.45
15.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-9430.12	0	
16				-5143.71		43946.77	21973.39
16.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-11144.7	0	
17				-6000.99		32802.07	16401.04
17.5	6412.9	7270.188	-857.288		-12859.3	0	
18				-6858.28		19942.8	9971.4
18.5	6526.4	6210	316.4		-13400.2	0	
19				-6541.88		6542.64	3271.32
19.5	6866.92	325	6541.92		-6541.84	0	
20				0.04		0.8	0.4

Figure 22: Shear force diagram

Figure 23 : Bending moment diagram

CHAPTER 9

STABILIZING THE STRUCTURE

9.1: Applying constraints to the Model

To solve the model, the first step is to constraint it in the required direction. Constraints are used to restrict the model's movement in any of the three translational or three rotational degrees of freedom. In Maestro nodes of the model is selected first, which will be the require constraint points. In this thesis fore & aft side of the pontoon are constraints, to do that nodes of the main deck in the fore & aft portion is selected. Then the degrees of freedom of movement of the nodes are set. The first node of the main deck in fore of pontoon is constraint in the X, Y,Z direction. Then similarly the first node of the main deck in aft portion is constraint in the X, Y, Z direction. As the model has transverse symmetry, the model is constrained for rotation about the Y axis. The Y and Z constraints at both nodes restrict rotation about the X and Z axes. Thus, the constraints are set in the model.

9.2: Applying loads on the model

Loads are applied in the model by creating load case in the maestro. A load case consists of all of the loads which act on the structure at the same time. Loads which do not act simultaneously should be placed in separate load cases unless their interaction is negligible. Each load case produces a separate solution for the nodal displacements, and hence load effects, in the structure. In the example only one load case is applied and the only loads acting on it are its self-weight and the prescribed design bending moment. Load safety factor is 1, it includes structures mass that means self weight, gravitational force & end moment. Sagging bending moments are positive & hogging bending moments are negative & shear forces are positive at both ends . sagging moment is applied in this case which is of value 10901.5Nm at both reference end & opposite end. After balancing is done on the model which is only for vertical bending at structural coordinates, shear force is automatically calculated on the model. At reference end vertical shear force value is 925385N & at opposite end shear force has the value of 926587N.

Chapter 10

ANALYSIS OF THE MODEL

After constraints & balancing is done, the next step is to solve the model. In this thesis Global FEA method is selected, which has equation solver method Sparse, beam attached to the plating is considered as eccentric beams & failure mode evaluation is done by Maestro method.

After analyzing the model, deformations are represented as following:

Figure 24 : model deformation under load

Side deformations are also occurred at the sides of longitudinal bulkhead:

Figure 25 : side deformation under load

In the output window maximum displacement is found 0.00138239 m.

The stress patterns can be viewed or specific stresses and displacements can be recovered then.

The normal stress distribution at X axis is as following:

Figure 26 : normal stress distribution at X axis of pontoon

The normal stress distribution at Y axis is as following:

Figure 27 : normal stress distribution at Y axis of pontoon

The shear stress distribution at XY axis is as following:

Figure 28 : shear stress distribution at XY axis of pontoon

The Von Mises stress distribution of the structure is as following:

Figure 29 : Von mises stress distribution of pontoon

From the dynamic query stress, displacements at specific nodes can be viewed at different strakes. At middle portion of the pontoon the values of one strake is shown as following :

Figure 30 : dynamic query at middle of the pontoon

At fore portion of the pontoon the values of one strake are shown as following:

Figure 31 : dynamic query at bow of the pontoon

At aft portion of the pontoon the values of one strake is shown as following:

Figure 32 : dynamic query at stern of the pontoon

Failure mode evaluation is performed on evaluation patches in the model. During the analysis of the model, MAESTRO automatically created evaluation patches. A patch is a collection of elements with its boundary supported by bulkheads or beams. A patch can also be a single element. The created patches of the pontoon is displayed as following:

Figure 33 : distribution of patches in the pontoon

There is an adequacy parameter in Maestro to check the ‘serviceability’ of the design. The portion of the structure which have negative adequacy means that the structure is under built & would fail under the prescribed load. So to investigate which members are falling adequacy parameter is of great help. We can see that our model has no negative adequacy anywhere under this load case:

Figure 34 : adequacy of the model

This is the display of the Maestro calculated ‘modeled weight’. Modeled weight means the weight calculated by maestro based on the materials& elements that make-up the FE model.

Figure 35 : self-weight of the model

Below is the distribution of the bending moment distribution of the FE model. We can see that the distribution is of similar characteristics of the BM curve obtained by tabular method with a peak at amidship :

Figure 36 : bending moment distribution of the model

Along with the vertical distribution, maestro also shows the horizontal distribution of SF& BM. The horizontal distribution of shear force& bending moment is given below:

Figure 37 : distribution of shear force (horizontal)

Figure 38 : distribution of bending moment (horizontal)

If we select the properties & results in output, Maestro automatically creates a MS excel file of the selected output data. this is the gross weight& bending moment output from the excel file:

Figure: gross weight of the model

Figure: bending moment of the model

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In this thesis analysis of a marine vehicle naming pontoon is done, to find out the deformation, stress distribution, adequacy parameters & patches of the structure under its self weight which causes a bending moment in the structure of amount of 10901.5257 N-m. the maximum displacement of the pontoon is 0.0013823 m, which occurs in the midship. From the analysis it is found that the maximum value of normal X stress is $1.35e^{07}$ N/m² which occurs in bow&aft position & the minimum value of normal X stress is found $-7.45e^{06}$ N/m² which occurs in the upper deck of pontoon. In case of normal Y stress maximum value is $5.93e^{06}$ N/m² which is found also in bow& stern position & the minimum value is $-3.10e^{06}$ N/m² is found in the upper corners of the pontoon. From the distribution of shear stress XY the maximum value of shear stress is found $9.19e^{06}$ N/m² at one side of the pontoon & the minimum value is found $9.21e^{06}$ N/m² at the other side of pontoon. Von mises stress distribution is also found in this analysis. The von Mises stress is used to predict yielding of materials under any loading condition from results of simple uniaxial tensile tests. The von Mises stress satisfies the property that two stress states with equal distortion energy have equal von Mises stress. The maximum value of von mises stress is $1.87e^{07}$ N/m² which is found on the lower portion of pontoon & the minimum value of von mises stress is $1.28e^{03}$ N /m² which is found on the upper portion of the pontoon.

From the analysis the deformation of the pontoon structure is found, there is also side deformation in the structure. As the analysis gives a colored contour it is really helpful to easily distinguish the portion where maximum stress occurs, which is of utmost important for the preliminary design of a structure. Found from the analysis the values of maximum displacement are not a large one to contribute any chance to the collapse of the structure.

ANALYSIS, CONCLUSION& FUTURE RESEARCH:

Structural analysis of floating structure can be done using many available numerical investigations commercial software. In this thesis analysis of a pontoon has been done by using maestro marine software, the structural response analysis provides stress and displacement results for the entire vessel. Stresses are reported in the GUI; results can be queried and echoed to the output window. Maestro has the ability to align stress vectors in a uniform direction when recovering stress in a given axis.

In maestro evaluation is automatic - all structural members are evaluated to the factors of safety chosen by the user. Different factors of safety can be specified for all “collapse” limit states and for all “serviceability” limit states, or specified on a limit state-by-limit state basis. In this thesis, safety factor for collapse is chosen 1.5 & safety factor for all is chosen 1.25. as the values of displacement found by the analysis is within the allowable limits. From the distribution of shear stress, normal stress,von mises stress further stiffening can be done to the model if necessary.

FUTURE RESEARCH:

To have a optimal design which had a minimum self weight with the required strength can be done further by re-meshing & changing the formation of the structure from the previous of the pontoon. Failure mode analysis can be done using Maestro-marine software. failure modes address yielding, buckling, and other major failure modes typically found in design criteria. There are a total of 25 failure modes at the individual principal structural member level, and 10 at the overall or multi-member level. The failure analysis provides a quantified evaluation of each of these failure modes for each principal structural member, for each load case that is being analyzed. This result in a high level of information that identifies structural problems associated with events such as buckling. These structural failure evaluations are used by the structural engineer to assess the adequacy or degree of conservatism that is represented by the design. A fully integrated sea keeping and hydrodynamic loads prediction module naming MAESTRO-Wave which calculates and maps the dynamic pressures to the structural mesh for a user-defined set of speeds, headings and wave definitions.

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